

The Effect of Company's Culture and Dynamic Capability toward Company's Innovation and Performance on F&B SME in Surabaya

Hananiel M. Gunawan & Oliandes Sondakh

Abstract:

The dynamics and intensity of competition in business and among companies are increasing over time. This issue forced businesses to improve their capabilities, especially to achieve the goals and improve their performances. Food and beverage industries play a huge role in Indonesia's economy, particularly in SMEs. Food and Beverage industry is chosen because this industry requires a strategic position and various capabilities to be able to survive the competition. The purpose of this study is to examine the influence of company's culture and dynamic capabilities and their effects on innovation capabilities and performances. This study used 120 medium-sized enterprises in the food and beverage industry as a sample by using a random sampling method. The hypothesis testing method uses structural model equations to test 5 hypotheses in this study. The results showed that company's culture and dynamic capabilities should have a significant impact on company's ability to innovate and their performance as well.

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About Author (s)

Hananiel M. Gunawan (corresponding author), Lecturer, Business School, Universitas Pelita Harapan (Surabaya Campus), Indonesia.

Oliandes Sondakh, Lecturer, Business School, Universitas Pelita Harapan (Surabaya Campus), Indonesia.

Introduction

The dynamics of the economy and business are currently developing very quickly, where the competition is getting tougher. In the regional environment, currently Indonesia has implemented the ASEAN Economic Community which has implications for the economy and the business world in Indonesia, both for large and medium scale companies. In this case, medium-sized businesses have a strategic role, because medium-sized enterprises are a transitional period that becomes a stepping stone for small businesses before becoming large-scale companies, so the problems faced by medium-sized businesses are much more complex when compared to small businesses (Anggraini & Nasution, 2017).

One of the important points in the National Long-Term Development Plan (RPJPN) 2005 – 2025 is the policy on increasing the competitiveness of medium-sized enterprises so that they can grow sustainably. The government also provides support in the form of Law no. 20 of 2008 which became the legal umbrella to ensure the existence of medium-sized businesses in Indonesia to encourage economic growth, social stability and employment. Data from the Central Statistics Agency (2019) shows that medium-sized enterprises absorb 3.73 million workers, which is higher than the absorption rate of large enterprises which absorb 3.58 million people. Medium-sized businesses have also been proven to be more able to withstand the economic crisis, because unlike large companies, medium-sized businesses do not depend on capital or loans from abroad, especially in foreign currencies, so that when fluctuations in exchange rates occur, they will not have much impact on the economy. medium business. In this case, medium-sized enterprises show their role as one of the strong pillars of the economy. These various advantages have prompted the government to develop medium-sized enterprises in Indonesia, including the decentralization policy that makes each region have a strategic role.

In terms of explaining performance, the field of strategic management is dominated by two main theories, namely the Industrial Organization (Porter, 1981) and the Resource Based View (Barney, 1991). Several previous studies have shown that external factors can indeed explain the performance of medium-sized enterprises but not up to 20% of the performance variance (Caloghirou et al., 2004; Bmiatzi & Hall, 2009). Thus, empirical findings show that external factors are only able to explain the performance of no more than 20%. On the other hand, internal factors can explain the performance variance with a higher proportion of 66% (Kanyurhi et al., 2016) and even 84% (Mitrega & Maciej, 2012). Meanwhile, recent research (Fernandez et al., 2019) shows that the company's internal factors are indeed more dominant in explaining business performance in medium-sized businesses compared to external factors. Thus, the RBV approach can explain performance better than the Industrial Organization approach, so the basic theory to be developed in this research is the RBV approach.

The RBV approach emphasizes the importance of the resources and capabilities possessed by the company to be able to create and maintain its competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). Resources can be tangible or intangible that is used by the company to implement its strategy (Peteraf, 1993). Previous research has shown that intangible resources have more contribution to company performance than tangible resources (Wiklund & Shepherd, 2003; Mavondo et al., 2005). Intangible resources can be in the form of knowledge, innovation, leadership, organizational culture, communication, social networks, organizational reputation and others (Wojciechowska, 2016). This is in accordance with the requirement that a valuable resource must be a resource that is rare and difficult to imitate by competitors (Newbert, 2007) where intangible resources are more difficult to obtain because it takes longer than physical resources (Akhtar et al. al., 2008).

The world today has entered a new phase called the "New Economic Age" which is full of information and knowledge, leaving the old industrial era characterized by machine mechanization (Chiu et al., 2003). Therefore, there is a shift in the change in resource requirements, from tangible resources to intangible resources. Likewise, medium-sized enterprises are expected to be able to realize these needs by optimizing their intangible resources. However, the phenomenon in the field still shows that medium-sized enterprises in the snack food industry in East Java are currently still trapped in a paradigm that still relies on physical resources to compete, where there are still many who have not implemented a good organizational and management system so they are unable to access information and adequate knowledge (Hasanuddin & Aryanto, 2019). Various problems faced by medium-sized businesses include lack of capital, lack of managerial ability, no formal form of the company, and weak business networks (Anggraini & Nasution, 2017). In addition to these things, there is also unfair competition and economic pressure, resulting in a limited scope of business. Internally, medium-sized enterprises face more and more limitations, including capital, production techniques, market share, management, and technology, as well as weak decision-making and financial supervision and low competitiveness (Prasetyo, 2018).

Theoretical Basis

Company's Culture

According to Dawson (2017) organizational culture is a number of shared assumptions, beliefs, and values that can influence the thoughts and actions of each member. According to Robbins (2014) organizational culture is a belief that is believed together in a group, in which there is tolerance for a risk that is carried out, support from management, system imbalances and tolerance for problems that occur. With strong values embedded in an organization, it will have a positive impact on the sustainability of the organization. Meanwhile, according to Kreitner and Kinicki (2005), organizational culture is the social attachment between members of the organization, so that a characteristic or personality differences between one person with another person can united in an organizational force. Company's culture can be expressed as a pattern beliefs, values and ways of learning face the experiences that have been developed throughout the history of the organization and manifested in material arrangements and organizational member behavior (Wirawan, 2007). Culture can be defined as an entity that consists in how people think, feel, react, and also transmit thoughts that create a pattern. The main core of company's culture lies in its construct within its traditional ideas and also their attached values. Mouritsen (2015) defines company's culture as values, ideology, philosophy, trust, rituals, symbols, and norms that affect performance. Organizational culture is a phenomenon that is difficult to define. Schein (2012) offers a model for understanding organizational culture by dividing it into three levels, namely visible manifestations, values, and basic underlying assumptions. Pflesser & Homburg (2000) developed Schein's (2012) model by dividing organizational culture into four interrelated components, namely shared basic values, norms, artifacts and behaviors.

Through this definition, it can be seen the role of organizational culture as a "compass" that directs members within the organization. Organizational culture can also be a pattern of beliefs in the form of symbols or rituals that continue to change following organizational developments (Pheysey, 2013). Based on this definition, there are several main elements, namely organizational culture is a common phenomenon within the group, organizational culture has visible and invisible characteristics, each member in the group tries to learn organizational culture and organizational culture changes slowly over time. time (Baumgartner, 2009). Organizational culture becomes a guideline about what things are

considered important, how to give an assessment of something that is good or bad (Owen et al., 2000). Leaders or managers have an important role in shaping and maintaining culture within the organization (Andriopoulos, 2001). Organizational culture can be a source for a company's competitive advantage because organizational culture is a resource that is of high value and difficult for competitors to imitate because of its tacit and complex characteristics (Coyne, 1986).

Dynamic Capability

According to Ambrosini & Bowman (2009), the concept of dynamic capability is a the ability or continuation of the Resource Based View Theory. Although rooted in RBV theory, the dynamic capability approach has a different focus, namely on how valuable resources can be created, acquired, and maintained over time (Teece, 2014). The dynamic capability approach is rooted in managerial capabilities and organizational processes, in terms of coordination, integration, reconfiguration and transformation of owned resources. (Lei et al., 2016; Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000). According to Barney (1991), a company can gain a competitive advantage, if the company is able to master the resources that can be used to create value that distinguishes it from other companies. This concept is known as RBV. In addition, companies must also be able to develop capabilities through a series of mechanisms, systems, and expertise to develop resources, where these capabilities must be difficult to imitate by competitors (Dutta et al., 2003). However, Phatak (2010) states that the business environment is developing very quickly and is complex so that depending only to resources is not enough. Therefore, companies must develop different capabilities to be able to take advantage of the resources they have (Prange & Verdier, 2011). This concept is the basis for dynamic capabilities. The dynamic capabilities perspective is derived from the RBV concept and focuses on resource creation. Dynamic capabilities combined with a good strategy are the keys to success for the company to be able to maintain its sustainable performance, especially in a rapidly changing global environment. This dynamic capability is very important for companies in facing an environment that is developing very quickly, an increasingly fierce global competition environment and very fast technological changes (Teece, 2014).

Innovation capability

There are various definitions of innovation capability in the literature. Some researchers use the term innovation ability to reflect the level of innovation or organizational innovation or innovation (Wonglimpiyarat, 2010; Laforet, 2011; Withers et al., 2011). The ability of innovation is the ability of a company to change ideas from nothing to something new that brings economic value. While value can relate to wealth and performances. Economic value will increase profits and consequently company performance (Withers, Drnevich, and Marino, 2011). According to Ngah and Ibrahim (2011), innovation capability refers to the company's will and ability to create and generate knowledge, usually in the aspect or form of intellectual property. This can be shown by a pattern that has benefits for the organization. Innovation refers to the creation of new value for the company, its stakeholders, and customers (Bolisani, 2017). An idea or invention only becomes an innovation if it can be used and has the potential to be realized effectively. Therefore, innovative ability is defined as the ability to continuously seek for knowledge and ideas and transform them into new products. Thus, new product can lead to better process and system for efficiency purposes (Ho, 2017). Innovation is a series of process of turning knowledge into something that has value through the implementation of better product, better systems and better process. The term innovativeness often defined to better understand and indicate the degree of novelty from an update or a given innovation (Garcia and Calantone, 2012), or the extent to which a company or individual adopts something new (Hurt et al., 2011).

Business Performance

Business performance is an important factor that is of concern to many managers because it is an indicator to assess the success of a company in implementing its strategy in achieving company goals (Werther et al., 2005; Sellani, 2014). Therefore, business performance measurement is a very common theme discussed in various literatures on strategic management (Ford & Schellenberg, 1982). According to Tsamenyi et al. (2010), business performance is defined as "extent of a firm's efficiency, which is different from target achievement". Through this concept there are two important factors that define business performance. First is the issue of efficiency. The second is the problem of comparing the company's achievements with the targets to be achieved. According to Torres (2018), business performance is how the company can absorb and fully deploy its assets to create revenues, and usually its measured in monetary terms". According to Prange & Verdier (2011), there are two important factors in measuring performance, namely growth and profitability.

The effect of Company's Culture on Company's Innovation

According to Covin & Slevin (2010), the ability of an organization to develop an entrepreneurial orientation depends on the culture of the organization. This is also supported by Zahra et al. (2019) that the design of organizational culture is very important for the development of an entrepreneurial orientation. According to Hayton et al. (2002), cultural values can be an indicator for people to determine entrepreneurial behavior, such as risk taking and independent thinking. Research conducted by Morris et al. (2010) in the United States showed that there is a strong relationship between entrepreneurial performance or activity and cultural values, namely independence, freedom, and achievement. Another study conducted by McGrath et al (2013) in 10 countries showed that cultural values influence entrepreneurial behavior. Research by Chirico & Nordqvist (2010) found that companies that have a high level of knowledge and a more open culture will be better able to encourage entrepreneurial behavior compared to companies that have a closed culture. Therefore, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H1: Company's Culture has a significant effect on Company's Innovation

The effect of Dynamic Capability on Company's Innovation

Dynamic Capability is the most central and influential theory in the development of strategic management (Teece, 2007). Dynamic Capability has been a focus with significant growth, and its systematic reviews also deepened and widely used in meta-analytical studies (Di Stefano, Peteraf, & Verona, 2010; Eriksson, 2014) highlight that this stream of research still needs to be addressed. further researched. The main principle of the dynamic capabilities view is that dynamic capabilities are positively related to a firm's competitive advantage and successful performance (Barreto, 2010). Several researchers have attempted to develop this theory (eg, Fainshmidt et al., 2016; Pezeshkan, Fainshmidt, Nair, Frazier, & Markowski, 2016) highlighting the positive relationship between dynamic ability and performance outcomes. Amit and Schoemaker (2018) define organizational capability as the capacity to use existing resources and use organizational processes to achieve the desired goals. Companies that have dynamic capabilities and can integrate and transfer knowledge resources, and their impact get better performance.

Macher and Mowery's (2009) provided a research results in the context of semiconductor manufacturing. The researcher believed that dynamic ability of companies to introduce new process technologies is found that the introduction of new process technologies that are more effective will further improve company performance. Dynamic Capability Theory seeks to explain organizational performance as a function of the company's ability to change its

resources in an effort to achieve the desired company performance (Torres, 2108). This focus is considered beneficial and useful based on the environmental change that changes rapidly. Thus, Dynamic Capability Theory has been suggested as a foundation that can provide better understanding for companies and corporate strategic values (Drnevich and Croson 2013; Pavlou and El Sawy 2010, 2011).

H2: Dynamic Capability has a significant effect on Company's Innovation

According to Helfat & Martin (2015), dynamic capabilities are needed by companies to create a company innovation. The dynamic capability to absorb knowledge effectively is the key for companies to be more innovative (Cepeda-Carrion et al., 2012). Companies that are able to manage information and knowledge will be able to identify new opportunities (Helfat & Martin, 2015). Dynamic capabilities enable companies to absorb the information needed by the company so that companies become more proactive in taking action compared to competitors (Liao et al., 2003). Companies that have dynamic capabilities will be able to anticipate the steps taken by competitors, and improve the quality of decision making so as to enable employees to act independently in taking the opportunities that exist (Green et al., 2008). Companies with high dynamic capabilities tend to have more routine communication habits among their employees which helps them to share and combine various views on new opportunities and are able to respond to any opportunities in the market (Rothaermel & Alexander, 2009). Companies with high dynamic capabilities will also be able to explore new opportunities more efficiently than their competitors so that they are able to be superior when compared to their competitors (Engelen et al., 2014). This is also supported by Barreto (2010) which states that dynamic capabilities are needed by company management to be able to identify market trends so that they are able to adjust resources, processes, and organizational structures to deal with possible changes that occur. This makes the company able to take opportunities by adjusting the company's conditions according to consumer needs.

The effect of Company's Culture on Business Performance

The influence of organizational culture on performance has been widely studied using various models and constructs (Ogbonna & Harris, 2000; Poll, 2000) where it has been proven that organizational culture can be a source of competitive advantage (Scholz, 1987; Krefting & Frost, 1985). Deshpande & Farley (2018) found that organizational culture is the key to success for companies in India and Japan in carrying out their business strategies. Research by Kotter & Heskett (2015) found that organizational culture has a significant effect on the company's financial performance in the long term. However, Sadri & Lees (2001) also found that a positive organizational culture can bring many non-financial benefits to the organization, thereby creating a competitive advantage for the company compared to other companies in its industry. This shows that organizational culture does not have a positive impact on financial performance only, but also non-financial. According to Jogaratnam (2017), organizational culture has a significant effect on performance, both financial and non-financial. This is supported by various other studies (Onken, 2010; Rashid et al., 2003; Tseng & Lee 2012; Pickles and Pickles, 2012; Gambi et al., 2015; Valmohammadi & Roshanzamir, 2015; Husseina, et al., 2016 ; Laforet, 2016; Nazarian et al., 2017; Savović, 2017; Dirisu et al., 2018; Maamari & Saheb, 2018). However, recent research by Zhao et al. (2018) shows that organizational culture has a negative and significant effect on business performance. Meanwhile, fewer studies have shown that organizational culture has no significant effect on business performance (Agbejule, 2011; Yesil & Kaya, 2013; Harwiki, 2016; Valencia et al., 2016; Shanker & Bhanugopan, 2017).

H3: Company's Culture has a significant effect on Business Performance

The effect of Dynamic Capability on Business Performance

The concept of dynamic capabilities has been widely studied as a determinant of company performance that distinguishes companies from one another (Zott, 2003). According to Griffith et al. (2016), companies that have dynamic capabilities will be able to integrate their knowledge resources so that they are able to produce better performance. Research by O'Reilly & Tushman (2008) found that dynamic capabilities enable companies to manage their resources to keep costs low and keep asset utilization high so as to improve company performance. Teece's research (2014) found that dynamic capabilities enable companies to be able to obtain superior performance in the long term. Regarding financial performance, Drnevich & Kriauciunas (2010) found that dynamic capabilities actually have a negative and significant effect on performance, because of the costs that must be incurred by the company to obtain dynamic capabilities, but it is emphasized in this study that there is a time lag before dynamic capabilities are correct. - can actually provide positive benefits for the company's financial performance in the future. This means that in the short term, dynamic capabilities have a negative effect on financial performance, but in the long term, dynamic capabilities will have a positive effect. In contrast to that, Zott (2003) found that dynamic capabilities actually have a positive effect on the company's financial performance (profitability) as long as the company is able to manage the costs to obtain these dynamic capabilities. Wang & Kwei's research (2017) finds that dynamic capabilities have a significant effect on company performance in the manufacturing industry because dynamic capabilities enable companies to respond quickly to changes in the business environment. Another study (Protogerou et al., 2011) found that dynamic capability is a factor that has a significant effect on performance, even more significantly than the operational capabilities of companies in the manufacturing industry. Research Makkonen et al. (2013) found that dynamic capabilities remain a significant antecedent to business performance, even in crisis conditions.

Research by Robert & Grover (2011) shows that dynamic capabilities have a positive and significant effect on business performance. This is supported by various other studies (Tseng and Lee, 2012; Makkonen et al., 2013; Wilden et al., 2013; Hofer et al., 2015; Pinho & Prange, 2015; Wamba et al., 2016; Kamariah et al., 2016). al., 2017; Mikalef & Pateli, 2017; Wilden & Gudergan, 2017; Torres et al., 2018). Meanwhile, fewer studies show that dynamic capabilities have no significant effect on business performance (Nedzinskis et al., 2013; Simon et al., 2015; Hong & Ding, 2017; Kuo et al., 2017; Ringov, 2017).

H4: Dynamic Capability has a significant effect on Business Performance

The effect of Company Innovation on Business Performance

The effect of innovation on business performance remains a topic of interest to researchers. Zain (2012) argues that innovation is an opportunity for companies to gain competitive advantage. By offering innovative products or services, companies can sometimes avoid price competition, access new marketing and create new demands, and improve company performance. Through successful innovation, customers will pay a premium price and buy more often increasing customer loyalty when the product or service purchased meets the wants or special needs of the customer (Moreau & Herd, 2010). In addition, innovation supports the company's efforts to prevent competitors from entering the market, strengthening their positional advantage thereby increasing their resilience to existing competition (Acosta, 2015). In their study involving insurance companies in China, Rajapathirana and Hui (2017) found significant differences between groups of companies. The results show that more innovative companies have greater potential value for their industry. Recent research indicates and proves that there is a positive and significant relationship

between innovation and business performance in various industrial midwives (Cheng, Yang, and Sheu (2014), Grisseemann, Plank, and Brunner-Sperdin (2013)).

In business environment, changes and uncertainties forces companies to seek and formulate strategic change and alternatiiegs (Lawrence and Lorsch, 2014). While strategies and alternatives are crucial aspects of business sustainability, innovation is another way to develop and overcome change to ensure the expected outcomes (Damanpour et al., 2009). Business will adopt its innovation to respond in so many changes, demands and also uncertainties, and this can. Researches has found that growth strategies can help companies to enter new markets and also increase their marketshare.(Gunday et al., 2018). Taiwan, Lin and Chen (2009) found innovation, particularly innovation administration, to be the most important factor in explaining increased sales.

H5: Company Innovation has a significant effect on Business Performance

Research Model

Research Methodology

$$CI = b1. CC + b2.DC$$

$$BP = b3.CC + b4.DC + b5.CI$$

Data Analysis

The questionnaires were distributed, and 100 questionnaires were qualified to be processed for a further analysis. This result will give a better understanding of the impact of company’s culture and dynamic capability toward company’s innovation and business performance. The respondents for the study are the owners of food and beverage industry in Surabaya.

Table 1. Multiple Regression for Company’s Culture and Dynamic Capability on Company’s Innovation for F&B Industry

Model/ Variabel	R	Adj R ²	F _{Sig}	Standardized Coefficient Beta	Tsig	Hypothesis
CC,DC*CI	.848 ^a	.718	.000 ^b	0.156	.043	Supported
				0.963	.000	Supported

Source: Processed Data (2021)

Based on the analysis of Multiple Regression of for Company’s Culture and Dynamic Capability on Company’s Innovation for F&B Industry, the R value is 0.848 and this means that there is a strong correlation between independent variables and dependent variables. The adjusted R square value of 0.718 indicated that Company’s Culture and Dynamic Capability are able to

explain 71.8% of company innovation , while remaining 28.2% is influenced by other variables not included in this research. The Ftest value shows a significance value of 0.000 for CC and 0.043 for DC which means that the research model is accepted. Based on table 1, we can explain the following regression equation

$$CI = b_1 \cdot CC + b_2 \cdot DC$$

The positive coefficient indicates a direct change between the independent variable and the dependent variable . while a negative coefficient indicates the change is not the direction of the independent variables toward dependent variables. From the Ttest, we can conclude that

1. Company's Culture (CC) has a significant effect on Company's Innovation accepted at level of significance of 0.043 which is less than 0.05 benchmark
2. Dynamic Capability (DC) has a significant effect on Company's Innovation accepted at level of significance of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 benchmark

Table 2. Multiple Regression for Company's Culture and Dynamic Capability on Business Performance for F&B Industry

Model/ Variabel	R	Adj R ²	F _{Sig}	Standardized Coefficient Beta	Tsig	Hypothesis
CC,DC*BP	.947	.896	.000 ^b	0.115	.014	Supported
				0.855	.000	Supported

Source: Processed Data (2021)

Based on the analysis of Multiple Regression of for Company's Culture and Dynamic Capability on Business Performance for F&B Industry, the R value is 0.947 and this means that there is a strong correlation between independent variables and dependent variables. The adjusted R square value of 0.896 indicated that Company's Culture and Dynamic Capability are able to explain 89.6% of Business Performance, while remaining 10.4% is influenced by other variables not included in this research. The Ftest value shows a significance value of 0.014 for CC and 0.000 for DC which means that the research model is accepted. Based on table 1, we can explain the following regression equation

$$BP = b_3 \cdot CC + b_4 \cdot DC$$

The positive coefficient indicates a direct change between the independent variable and the dependent variable . while a negative coefficient indicates the change is not the direction of the independent variables toward dependent variables. From the Ttest, we can conclude that

1. Company's Culture (CC) has a significant effect on Business Performance accepted at level of significance of 0.014 which is less than 0.05 benchmark
2. Dynamic Capability (DC) has a significant effect on Business Performance accepted at level of significance of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 benchmark

Table 3. Simple Regression for Company Innovation on Business Performance for F&B Industry

Model/ Variabel	R	Adj R ²	F _{Sig}	Standardized Coefficient Beta	Tsig	Hypothesis
CI*BP	.573	.569	.000 ^b	0.	.000	Supported

Source: Processed Data (2021)

Based on the analysis of Multiple Regression of for Company's Innovation on Business Performance for F&B Industry, the R value is 0.573 and this means that there is a strong correlation between independent variables and dependent variables. The adjusted R square value of 0.569 indicated that Company's Innovation are able to explain 56.9% of Business Performance, while remaining 43.1% is influenced by other variables not included in this research. The Ftest value shows a significance value of 0.000 which means that the research model is accepted. Based on table 1, we can explain the following regression equation
 $BP = b_5 \cdot CI$

The positive coefficient indicates a direct change between the independent variable and the dependent variable. While a negative coefficient indicates the change is not the direction of the independent variables toward dependent variables. From the Ttest, we can conclude that Company's Innovation (CI) has a significant effect on Business Performance accepted at level of significance of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 benchmark

Discussion

Based on the results explained, we can see that the multiple regression analysis for this study provides an interesting insights and explanation. The first hypothesis which this study wants to know is the significance effect of company's culture toward company's innovation and the results has a positive and significant effect. This is consistent with the research results conducted by Ha and Stoel, 2012; Chen and Wells, 2019 which state that the company culture significantly impacted the ability of a company to innovate and increase the ability of the company innovation. For second hypothesis, the dynamic capability of a company is a crucial aspect in order for the company to be successful and thrive in the competing era. (Babin, Dardin, and Griffin, 2014). Based on the result provided, the dynamic capability can provide a significant impact on company's innovation. This is aligned with the study conducted by Achmed (2012) on tourism industry. The third hypothesis stated that the company's culture has a significant effect on business performance, and the data shows that company's culture does affect how employees work, the better environment, and supportive surroundings can increase the work and goals achieved. The fourth hypothesis that states dynamic capability has significant effect on business performance, and based on the data provided, dynamic capability does provide a good sense of how employees should maneuver and allocate their resources based on the surrounding and the consumers need. This would effect performance of the company. The last hypothesis stats that the innovation of a company would significantly effect the performance, due to increasing knowledge, increasing innovation skills, this will impact the performance of a business.

Conclusion

This model is quite simple in terms of the numbers of variables studied but analyzing with one of the most agile industry during pandemic, food and beverage industry can be seen as an interesting industry to be analyzed. The research model in this study is developed to deepen our knowledge and increase our understanding of how business should perform, given the independent variables that affect is our company's culture, dynamic capability, and company's innovation. This research model is formed from the relationship between. Based on the data calculations and results, we can draw conclusion that the company's culture does improve employees to be creative and improve their innovation skills, better working environment also improves performance of the company as a whole. While most companies focus on marketing strategies, and other promotion strategies, this study focuses on the internal environment and

capabilities, such as better working environment as a part of company's culture, and also how flexible and agile a company should be, as a part of dynamic capability. Especially in food and beverage industry, this industry should maintain their ability and also increase their skills to achieve the goals in the midst of uncertainties and tight competitions. Thus, food and beverage industries should constantly increase their agility by providing necessary tools, such as applying standard operational procedure, providing trainings and developments for employees, providing quality food and beverage related to the what the competitors are offering. These methods will maintain and balance the cost occurred and increase work quality output. Further research can be widened within the given scope or even broaden the respondents chosen into different areas and territories. This future result will provide interesting and meaningful implications, suggestions, and also conclusions. Especially for F&B owners, this study should be handy and provide guidance, in terms of what to do on internally. The future goal is that on further research carried out can deepen and provide better understanding on consumers behavior and also how to manage an organization.

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CC DC to CI

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1		.718	.714	.3140

a. Predictors: (Constant), DC, CC

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	30.681	2	15.340	155.556	.000 ^b
	Residual	12.031	122	.099		
	Total	42.712	124			

a. Dependent Variable: CI

b. Predictors: (Constant), DC, CC

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.625	.240		2.601	.010
	CC	-.183	.090	-.156	-2.043	.043
	DC	1.030	.082	.963	12.624	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CI

CC DC to BP

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.947 ^a	.897	.896	.20286699440 7658

a. Predictors: (Constant), DC, CC

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	43.845	2	21.922	532.679	.000 ^b
	Residual	5.021	122	.041		
	Total	48.866	124			

a. Dependent Variable: BP

b. Predictors: (Constant), DC, CC

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.580	.155		-3.733	.000
	CC	.145	.058	.115	2.507	.014
	DC	.979	.053	.855	18.557	.000

a. Dependent Variable: BP

CI to BP

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.757 ^a	.573	.569	.412081602716880

a. Predictors: (Constant), CI

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.979	1	27.979	164.765	.000 ^b
	Residual	20.887	123	.170		
	Total	48.866	124			

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